

Off-axis tensile creep deformation in unidirectional carbon/epoxy laminates

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Abstract

In the present study, tensile tests and creep tests of unidirectional CFRP laminates are performed at off-axis angles (15° , 30° , 45° , 60° , 75°) and 90° . The purpose of this study is to model the nonlinear behavior and creep deformation behavior. A CFRP material used is T700S/2500 carbon/epoxy system. The specimen size is 120mm long, 10mm wide and 0.74mm thick. The tests are performed at room (25°C) and high (65°C) temperatures. In the creep tests, constant tensile stresses of 30MPa and 38MPa are applied on the specimens for 400 minutes. A biaxial strain gage is mounted at the center of a specimen to measure time-strain relation. The creep compliance increases rapidly for the specimen with large off-axis angles. To model the creep behavior, an effective creep compliance model is applied. It is found that the strain-time behavior in unidirectional laminate can be described by the effective creep compliance model.

INTRODUCTION

Due to the anisotropy of unidirectional composite laminates, the strength and stiffness of off-axis specimens are low compared to those in the fiber direction. Moreover, it is known that fiber composites exhibit nonlinear stress-strain response under off-axis loading [1-7]. In order to make good use of material properties, it is very important to understand the mechanical properties in off-axis direction accurately, because composite laminates are used as multidirectional laminates. On the other hand, it is reported that polymer matrix composites show creep behavior not only at higher temperatures but also at room temperature [2]. In the present study, tensile tests and creep tests of unidirectional laminates are performed at off-axis angles, 15° , 30° , 45° , 60° , 75° and 90° . The purpose of this study is to describe the nonlinear behavior of a CFRP composite laminate under off-axis tension and to characterize the effect of the temperature and stress on the creep deformation of unidirectional laminates. The concept of effective stress and effective strain was used to generate master creep compliance curves based on the off-axis creep compliance curves. This model enables one to predict the creep compliance of the composite under the constant tensile loading.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

A CFRP material used is T700S/2500 carbon/epoxy system. Laminate configuration is 5 ply unidirectional laminate. The specimens of tensile test and creep test cut from a panel in 15° , 30° , 45° , 60° , 75° , and 90° directions. The specimen size of tensile and creep test specimens is 120mm long, 10mm wide and 0.74mm thick. Figure 1 shows the specimen configuration ((a) tensile test specimen, (b) creep test specimen). GFRP tabs are glued on both edges of the specimens. Tensile and creep test are performed on the specimens at the room (25°C) and high (65°C)

temperatures. For the tensile test, the crosshead speed is 0.5mm/min. The specimens are loaded until the final failure. For the creep test, constant tensile loads of 30MPa and 38MPa are applied to off-axis specimens for 400 minutes. Biaxial strain gages are mounted at the center of the specimens to measure stress-strain curves and strain-time curves, for tensile test and creep test, respectively.

Fig.1 Specimen configuration of (a) tensile test specimen and (b) creep test specimen
EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Tensile test

Figure 2 show the stress-strain curves of unidirectional laminates at room temperature (RT) and at high temperature (65°C). The unidirectional composite showed nonlinear stress-strain relations at all angles. It is seem that the nonlinearity is larger at higher temperature.

To model the nonlinear stress-strain relation, the one-parameter plasticity model proposed by Sun and Chen is applied [1]. Following the procedure in Ref. [1], it is assumed that the strains can be divided into two parts, that is, linear elastic and nonlinear parts.

$$\varepsilon = \varepsilon^e + \varepsilon^p \quad (1)$$

where superscripts e and p denote linear elasticity and nonlinearity, respectively.

It is also assumed that the nonlinear part comes from plasticity. In one-parameter plasticity model (eqs.(2)-(4)), we aim to obtain a parameter which lead to a master curve of the effective stress-effective plastic strain curve from the data of all angles. The effective stress and the effective plastic strain are obtained from the axial tensile stress and the axial nonlinear strain by using the following equations.

$$\bar{\sigma} = h(\theta)\sigma_x \quad (2)$$

$$\bar{\varepsilon}^p = \varepsilon^p / h(\theta) \quad (3)$$

where

$$h(\theta) = \left[\frac{3}{2} \{ \sin^4 \theta + 2a_{66} \sin^2 \theta \cos^2 \theta \} \right]^{1/2} \quad (4)$$

Figure 3 shows the effective stress-effective plastic strain curves for unidirectional laminate at RT and 65°C. It is seen that the curves from all off-axis angles gather on a single curve at each temperature. Initial longitudinal Young's moduli for all angles are listed in Table 1. The initial Young's moduli were used to determine the linear elastic strain. The plastic parameters obtained are shown in Table 2. We could show that it is independent of off-axis angles, a master curve is obtained, nonlinear behavior for unidirectional CFRP laminate are described by one-parameter plasticity model. Figure 4 shows the initial Young's modulus as a function of off-axis angle with comparison to the anisotropic elasticity theory.

Fig.2. Stress-strain curves for unidirectional T700S/2500 laminates. ((a) RT and (b)65°C)

Table 1 Initial longitudinal Young's modulus at RT and 65°C

θ	\square	0	15	30	45	60	75	90
Young's modulus	RT	110	41	20	13	11	9.8	9.8
(GPa)	65°C	\square	35	15	12	9.3	9	8.3

(a) RT

(b) 65°C

Fig.3 Effective stress-effective plastic strain curves for unidirectional T700S/2500. ((a) RT and (b) 65°C)

Fig. 4 Relation between Young's modulus and the loading angle at RT and 65°C

Table 2 Plasticity parameter for unidirectional T700S/2500 at RT and 65°C

	a_{66}	$A(MPa^{-n})$	n
RT	2.0	6.0×10^{-13}	6.0
65°C	2.0	1.2×10^{-13}	6.1

Table 3 and Figure 5 show the tensile strength of the unidirectional laminate as a function of off-axis angle. Comparison to the prediction using the Tsai-Hill failure criterion is shown in Fig.5.

Fig. 5 Relation between tensile the strength and the loading angle at RT and 65°C

Table 3 Tensile strength at R.T and 65°C

θ	\square	0	15	30	45	60	75	90
Tensile strength	RT	\square	208	115	81	75	47	62
(MPa)	65 \square	\square	137	78	61	53	37	39

Creep test

Figure 6 shows time-strain relation obtained by the creep tests for (a) RT, 30MPa, (b) RT, 38MPa, (c) 65°C 30MPa and (d) 65°C 38MPa. It is seen that the CFRP unidirectional laminate used in the present study shows tensile creep behavior at both RT and 65°C .

To model the creep behavior observed, the creep compliance model is used [4]. Following the procedure used in Ref.[4], we assumed that the strain can be divided into initial strain and creep strain as

$$\varepsilon = \varepsilon^i + \varepsilon^c \tag{5}$$

The creep compliance was obtained from the creep strain by subtracting the initial strain. Creep compliance is defined as the value which creep strain is divided by the constant stress applied. Figure 7 shows creep compliance-time curves for unidirectional laminate for (a) RT, 30MPa, (b) RT, 38MPa, (c) 65°C 30MPa and (d) 65°C 38MPa.

Now we assume that creep potential has the same form as the one-parameter plasticity model. The relation between the effective creep compliance and the creep compliance can be written by

$$\bar{S}^c = \frac{\bar{\varepsilon}^c(t)}{\sigma} = \frac{\varepsilon_x^c(t)}{\sigma_x} \frac{1}{h_c^2(\theta)} = \frac{S_x^c(t)}{h_c^2(\theta)} \quad (6)$$

where

$$h_c(\theta) = \left[\frac{3}{2} (\sin^4 \theta + 2a_{66}^c \sin^2 \theta \cos^2 \theta) \right]^{1/2} \quad (7)$$

Figure 8 shows the resulting effective creep compliance-time curves for the unidirectional laminates. It is found that the strain-time behavior in unidirectional laminate can be described by the effective creep compliance model.

Fig. 6 Strain-time curve for unidirectional T700S/2500. ((a) RT, 30MPa, (b) RT, 38MPa, (c) 65°C, 30MPa, (d) 65°C, 38MPa)

(a) RT, 30MPa

(b) RT, 38MPa

(c) 65°C, 30MPa

(d) 65°C, 38MPa

Fig.7 Relation between creep compliance and time. ((a) RT, 30MPa, (b) RT, 38MPa, (c) 65°C, 30MPa, (d) 65°C, 38MPa)

(a) RT, 30MPa

(b) RT, 38MPa

Fig.8 Relation between effective creep compliance and time. ((a) RT, 30MPa, (b) RT, 38MPa, (c) 65°C, 30MPa, (d) 65°C, 38MPa)

CONCLUSIONS

Effects of tensile and tensile creep loading angle on nonlinear stress-strain and creep strain-time behavior in unidirectional laminate are investigated. The following conclusions are obtained.

- (1) It is confirmed that nonlinear stress-strain behavior obtained from data of tensile test can be described by the one-parameter plasticity model.
- (2) It is shown that the creep behavior in unidirectional laminates under off-axis loading can be modeled by the creep compliance model.

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